

Relative Injective Modules and Relative Flat Modules

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Abstract—Let R be a ring, n a fixed nonnegative integer. The concepts of $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective and $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat modules, and then give some characterizations of these modules over left n -coherent rings are introduced. In addition, we investigate the left and right n - \mathcal{FI} -resolutions of R -modules by left (right) derived functors $\text{Ext}_n(-, -)$ ($\text{Tor}^n(-, -)$) over a left n -coherent ring, where n - \mathcal{FI} stands for the categories of all $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -modules. These modules together with the left or right derived functors are used to study the $(n, 0)$ -injective dimensions of modules and rings.

Keywords— $(n, 0)$ -injective module, $(n, 0)$ -injective dimension, $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective(flat) module, (Pre)cover, (Pre)envelope.

I. INTRODUCTION

THROUGHOUT this paper, n is a positive integer unless a special note. R denotes an associative ring with identity and all modules considered are unitary. M_R (${}_R M$) denotes a right(left) R -module. For an R -module M , $E(M)$ stands for the injective envelope of M , the character module $\text{Hom}_Z(M, Q/Z)$ is denoted by M^+ , and $\text{id}(M)$ ($\text{fd}(M)$) is the injective(flat) dimension of M .

B. Stenström [11] defined and studied FP-injective modules. FP-injective modules are also called absolutely pure modules[9], these modules have been studied by many authors. In the paper [11], right Noetherian rings, right coherent rings, right semihereditary rings and regular rings are characterized by FP-injective right R -modules. It has been recently proven that every left R -module has an FP-injective cover over a left coherent ring R in the paper [9]. On the other hand, every left R -module M has an FP-injective preenvelope over any ring in the paper [6]. In the paper [7], L.X.Mao and N.Q.Ding introduced the definitions of FI-injective and FI-flat modules and give some characterizations of these modules over left coherent rings. FI-injective and FI-flat modules together with the left derived functors of Hom are used to study the FP-injective dimensions of modules and rings.

As generalizations of the paper [7], we introduce the definitions of $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective and $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat modules and give some characterizations of these modules over left n -coherent rings. In addition, we investigate the left and right n - \mathcal{FI} -resolutions of R -modules by left (right) derived functors $\text{Ext}_n(-, -)$ ($\text{Tor}^n(-, -)$) over a left n -coherent ring, where n - \mathcal{FI} stands for the categories of all $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -modules. These modules together with the left

or right derived functors are used to study the $(n, 0)$ -injective dimensions of modules and rings.

We recall some known notions and facts needed in the sequel.

Let R be a ring and n be a non-negative integer. A left R -module M is called n -presented in case there is an exact sequence of left R -modules $F_n \rightarrow F_{n-1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow F_1 \rightarrow F_0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow 0$ in which every F_i is a finitely generated free [3], equivalently projective left R -module. Let n, d be non-negative integers. According to [13], a left R -module M is called (n, d) -injective(respectively (n, d) -flat) if $\text{Ext}^{d+1}(N, M) = 0$ (respectively $\text{Tor}_{d+1}(N, M) = 0$) for all n -presented left (respectively right) R -modules N . The $(n, 0)$ -injective($(n, 0)$ -flat) dimension of M [14], denoted by $(n, 0)\text{-id}(M)$ ($(n, 0)\text{-fd}(M)$), is defined to be the smallest nonnegative integer m such that $\text{Ext}^{m+1}(F, M) = 0$ ($\text{Tor}_{m+1}(F, M) = 0$) for every n -presented left R -module F (if no such m exists, set $(n, 0)\text{-id}(M)$ ($(n, 0)\text{-fd}(M)$) = ∞), and $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R)$ ($l.(n, 0)\text{-wdim}(R)$) is defined as $\sup\{(n, 0)\text{-id}(M)$ ($(n, 0)\text{-fd}(M)$) : M is a left R -module}.

Let \mathcal{C} be a class of R -modules and M an R -module. Following [5], we say that a homomorphism $\varphi : M \rightarrow C$ is a \mathcal{C} -preenvelope if $C \in \mathcal{C}$ and the abelian group homomorphism $\text{Hom}(\varphi, C') : \text{Hom}(C, C') \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, C')$ is surjective for each $C' \in \mathcal{C}$. A \mathcal{C} -preenvelope $\varphi : M \rightarrow C$ is said to be a \mathcal{C} -envelope if every endomorphism $g : C \rightarrow C$ such that $g\varphi = \varphi$ is an isomorphism. Dually we have the definitions of a \mathcal{C} -precover and a \mathcal{C} -cover. \mathcal{C} -envelopes (\mathcal{C} -covers) may not exist in general, but if they exist, they are unique up to isomorphism. A homomorphism $\varphi : M \rightarrow C$ with $C \in \mathcal{C}$ is said to a \mathcal{C} -envelope with the unique mapping property [5] if for any homomorphism $f : M \rightarrow C'$ with $C' \in \mathcal{C}$, there is a unique homomorphism $g : C \rightarrow C'$ such that $g\varphi = f$. Dually we have the definition of a \mathcal{C} -cover with the unique mapping property.

In what follows, we write ${}_R \mathcal{M}$ and $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ for the categories of all left R -modules and all $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -modules, respectively. According to Costa[7], a ring R is called a left n -coherent ring in case every n -presented left R -module is $(n + 1)$ -presented. It is easy to see that R is left 0-coherent(resp. 1-coherent) if and only if it is left noetherian(resp. coherent), and every n -coherent ring is m -coherent for $m \geq n$. n -coherent rings have been investigated by many authors(see Chen and Ding[1,4], Costa[3]). For $n \geq 1$, it has been proven that every left R -module M has an $(n, 0)$ -injective preenvelope over any ring in [8]. So M has a right n - \mathcal{FI} -resolution, that is, there is a $\text{Hom}(-, n\text{-}\mathcal{FI})$ exact complex $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow$

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... with each $F^i(n, 0)$ -injective. Obviously, the complex is exact. Let

$$L^0 = M, L^1 = \text{coker}(M \rightarrow F_0),$$

$$L^i = \text{coker}(F^{i-2} \rightarrow F^{i-1}) \quad \text{for } i \geq 2$$

The n th cokernel $L_n (n \geq 0)$ is called the n th n - \mathcal{FI} -cosyzygy of M .

On the other hand, for $n \geq 1$, it has been proven that every left R -module has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover over a left n -coherent ring R [8]. So every left R -module M has a left n - \mathcal{FI} -resolution, that is, there is a $\text{Hom}(n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}, -)$ exact complex $\cdots \rightarrow F_1 \rightarrow F_0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow 0$ (not necessarily exact) with each $F_i(n, 0)$ -injective. Write

$$K_0 = M, K_1 = \ker(F_0 \rightarrow M),$$

$$K_i = \ker(F_{i-1} \rightarrow F_{i-2}) \quad \text{for } i \geq 2.$$

The n th kernel $K_n (n \geq 0)$ is called the n th n - \mathcal{FI} -syzygy of M .

Note that $\text{Hom}(-, -)$ is left balanced on ${}_R\mathcal{M} \times_R \mathcal{M}$ by $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI} \times n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ for a left n -coherent ring R (see [6, Definition 8.2.13]). Thus the n th left derived functor of $\text{Hom}(-, -)$, which is denoted by $\text{Ext}_n(-, -)$, can be computed using a right n - \mathcal{FI} -resolution of the first variable or a left n - \mathcal{FI} -resolution of the second variable. Following [6, Definition 8.4.1], the left n - \mathcal{FI} -dimension of a left R -module M , denoted by $\text{left } n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}\text{-dim } M$, is defined as $\inf\{m : \text{there is a left } n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}\text{-resolution of the form } 0 \rightarrow F_m \rightarrow \cdots \rightarrow F_0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow 0 \text{ of } M\}$. If there is no such m , set $\text{left } n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}\text{-dim}(M) = \infty$. The global left n - \mathcal{FI} -dimension of ${}_R\mathcal{M}$, denoted by $\text{gl left } n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}\text{-dim } \mathcal{M}$, is defined to be $\sup\{\text{left } n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}\text{-dim}(M) : M \in {}_R\mathcal{M}\}$ and is infinite otherwise. The right versions can be defined similarly.

Recall that a left R -module M is called reduced [6] if M has no nonzero injective submodules.

In Section II of this paper, we introduce the concepts of $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective and $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat modules. It is shown that a left R -module M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective if and only if M is a kernel of an $(n, 0)$ -injective precover $A \rightarrow B$ with A injective. For a left n -coherent ring R , we prove that a left R -module M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective if and only if M is a direct sum of an injective left R -module and a reduced $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module; an n -presented right R -module M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat if and only if M is a cokernel of an $(n, 0)$ -flat preenvelope of a right R -module.

In Section III, we investigate the $(n, 0)$ -injective dimensions of modules and rings in terms of $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective and $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat modules and the left derived functors $\text{Ext}_n(-, -)$. Let R be a left n -coherent ring. We first give some characterizations of left n -hereditary rings. It is proven that R is left n -hereditary (i.e., $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R) \leq 1$) if and only if the canonical map $\sigma : \text{Ext}_0(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, N)$ is a monomorphism for all left R -modules M and N if and only if every $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module is injective if and only if every $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module is flat. Then it is shown that $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R) \leq m (m \geq 2)$ if and only if $\text{Ext}_{m+k}(M, N) = 0$ for all left R -modules M, N and all $k \geq -1$.

In Section IV, we first investigate that the $-\otimes-$ on $\mathcal{M}_R \times_R \mathcal{M}$ is right balanced by $n\text{-}\mathcal{F} \times n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ in the n -coherent ring, where $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ stands for the class of all $(n, 0)$ -flat modules. Then we introduce the right derived functors $\text{Tor}^n(-, -)$ and give some characteristic of right $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}\text{-dim } M$ and $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}\text{-dim } M$ for any R -module M in the n -coherent ring R .

Let M and N be R -modules. $\text{Hom}(M, N)$ (respectively $\text{Ext}^n(M, N)$) means $\text{Hom}_R(M, N)$ (respectively $\text{Ext}_R^n(M, N)$), and similarly $M \otimes_R N$ (respectively $\text{Tor}_n(M, N)$) denotes $M \otimes_R N$ (respectively $\text{Tor}_n^R(M, N)$) for an integer $n \geq 1$ throughout this paper. For unexplained concepts and notations, we refer the reader to [6, 10, 12].

II. $(n, 0)$ -FI-INJECTIVE MODULES AND $(n, 0)$ -FI-FLAT MODULES

Definition 1 A left R -module M is called $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective if $\text{Ext}^1(G, M) = 0$ for any $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module G .

A right R -module N is said to be $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat if $\text{Tor}_1(N, G) = 0$ for any $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module G .

Remark 1 (1) A right R -module M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat if and only if M^+ is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective by the standard isomorphism: $\text{Ext}^1(N, M^+) \simeq \text{Tor}_1(M, N)^+$ for any left R -module N .

(2) We note that by the above definitions that $(1, 0)$ -FI-injective (flat) modules are FI-injective (flat) module in [7] and any FI-injective (flat) module is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective (flat) for any $n \geq 1$.

Proposition 1 Let $\{M_i\}_I$ be family of right R -module

(1) $\bigoplus_I M_i$ is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat if and only if each M_i is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat;

(2) $\prod_I M_i$ is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective if and only if each M_i is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective.

Proof (1) By $\text{Tor}_1(G, \bigoplus_I M_i) \simeq \bigoplus_I \text{Tor}_1(G, M_i)$;

(2) By $\text{Ext}^1(G, \prod_I M_i) \simeq \prod_I \text{Ext}^1(G, M_i)$.

Definition 2 A ring R is said to be $(n, 0)$ -IP-ring if every $(n, 0)$ -injective R -module is projective; R is said to be $(n, 0)$ -IF-ring if every $(n, 0)$ -injective R -module is flat. It is trivial to show that if $n \geq n'$, then every $(n, 0)$ -IP(IF) ring is an $(n', 0)$ -IP(IF) ring and every $(0, 0)$ -IP-ring is a quasi-Frobenius ring and every $(0, 0)$ -IF-ring is an IF ring.

Next, we shall see that the class of right $(n, 0)$ -IP(IF) -rings contains several important known rings.

Proposition 2 Let R be a ring.

(1) R is a right $(n, 0)$ -IP-ring if and only if every right module is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective.

(2) R is a right $(n, 0)$ -IF-ring if and only if every left module is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat.

(3) If R is a right $(n, 0)$ -IP-ring, then R is a right $(n, 0)$ -IF-ring.

Proof Directly by the definitions.

Corollary 1 Let R be a ring.

(1) R is a right quasi-Frobenius if and only if every right module is FI-injective.

(2) R is a right IF-ring if and only if every left module is FI-flat.

(3) If R is a right quasi-Frobenius, then R is a right IF-ring.

Proposition 3 The following hold for a left n -coherent ring R :

(1) A left R -module M is injective if and only if M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective and $(n, 0)\text{-id}(M) \leq 1$.

(2) A right R -module N is flat if and only if N is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat and $(n, 0)\text{-fd}(N) \leq 1$.

Proof (1) "Only if" part is trivial.

"If" part. Let M be an $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module and $(n, 0)\text{-id}(M) \leq 1$. Then there is an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow E \rightarrow L \rightarrow 0$ with E injective. Note that L is $(n, 0)$ -injective by [14, Theorem 2.12] since R is a left n -coherent ring. So the exact sequence is split, and hence M is injective.

(2) "Only if" part is trivial.

"If" part. For any $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module N with $(n, 0)\text{-fd}(N) \leq 1$, we have N^+ is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective by Remark 2.2. Thus N^+ is injective by (1) since $(n, 0)\text{-id}(N^+) \leq 1$ by [14, Theorem 2.15]. So N is flat.

Proposition 4 The following are equivalent for a left R -module M :

(1) M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective.

(2) For every exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow E \rightarrow L \rightarrow 0$, where E is $(n, 0)$ -injective, $E \rightarrow L$ is an $(n, 0)$ -injective precover of L .

(3) M is a kernel of an $(n, 0)$ -injective precover $f : A \rightarrow B$ with A injective.

(4) M is injective with respect to every exact sequence $0 \rightarrow A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow 0$, where C is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2) and (1) \Rightarrow (4) are clear by definitions.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) is obvious since there exists a short exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow E(M) \rightarrow E(M)/M \rightarrow 0$.

(3) \Rightarrow (1) Let M be a kernel of an $(n, 0)$ -injective precover $f : A \rightarrow B$ with A injective. Then we have an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow A \rightarrow A/M \rightarrow 0$. So, for any $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module N , the sequence $\text{Hom}(N, A) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(N, A/M) \rightarrow \text{Ext}^1(N, M) \rightarrow 0$ is exact. It is easy to verify that $\text{Hom}(N, A) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(N, A/M) \rightarrow 0$ is exact by (3). Thus $\text{Ext}^1(N, M) = 0$, and so (1) follows.

(4) \Rightarrow (1). For each $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module N , there exists a short exact sequence $0 \rightarrow K \rightarrow P \rightarrow N \rightarrow 0$ with P projective, which induces an exact sequence $\text{Hom}(P, M) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(K, M) \rightarrow \text{Ext}^1(N, M) \rightarrow 0$. Note that $\text{Hom}(P, M) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(K, M) \rightarrow 0$ is exact by (4). Hence $\text{Ext}^1(N, M) = 0$, as desired.

Proposition 5 Let R be a left n -coherent ring. Then the following are equivalent for a left R -module M :

(1) M is a reduced $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module.

(2) M is a kernel of an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover $f : A \rightarrow B$ with A injective.

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2) By Proposition 4, the natural map $\pi : E(M) \rightarrow E(M)/M$ is an $(n, 0)$ -injective precover. Note that $E(M)/M$ has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover, and $E(M)$ has no nonzero direct summand K contained in M since M is reduced. It follows that $\pi : E(M) \rightarrow E(M)/M$ is an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover by [12, Corollary 1.2.8], and hence (2) follows.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Let M be a kernel of an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover $\alpha : A \rightarrow B$ with A injective. By Proposition 4, M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective. Now let K be an injective submodule of M . Suppose $A = K \oplus L$, $p : A \rightarrow L$ is the projection and $i : L \rightarrow A$ is the inclusion. It is easy to see that $\alpha(ip) = \alpha$ since $\alpha(K) = 0$. Therefore ip is an isomorphism since α is a cover. Thus i is epic, and hence $A = L$, $K = 0$. So M is reduced.

Theorem 1 Let R be a left n -coherent ring. Then a left R -module M is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective if and only if M is a direct sum of an injective left R -module and a reduced $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module.

Proof "If" part is clear.

"Only if" part. Let M be an $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module. Consider the exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow E(M) \rightarrow E(M)/M \rightarrow 0$. Note that $E(M) \rightarrow E(M)/M$ is an $(n, 0)$ -injective precover of $E(M)/M$ by Proposition 2.8. But $E(M)/M$ has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover $L \rightarrow E(M)/M$, so we have the commutative diagram with exact rows:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} 0 & \rightarrow & K & \xrightarrow{f} & L & \rightarrow & E(M)/M \rightarrow 0 \\ & & \downarrow \varphi & & \downarrow \gamma & & \parallel \\ 0 & \rightarrow & M & \xrightarrow{\alpha} & E(M) & \rightarrow & E(M)/M \rightarrow 0 \\ & & \downarrow \sigma & & \downarrow \beta & & \parallel \\ 0 & \rightarrow & K & \xrightarrow{f} & L & \rightarrow & E(M)/M \rightarrow 0 \end{array}$$

Note that $\beta\gamma$ is an isomorphism, and so $E(M) = \ker(\beta) \oplus \text{im}(\gamma)$. Thus L and $\ker(\beta)$ are injective (for $\text{im}(\gamma) \simeq L$). Therefore K is a reduced $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective module by Proposition 9. Since $\sigma\varphi$ is an isomorphism by the Five Lemma, we have $M = \ker(\sigma) \oplus \text{im}(\varphi)$, where $\text{im}(\varphi) \simeq K$. In addition, we get the commutative diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} & & 0 & & 0 & & 0 \\ & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ 0 & \rightarrow & \ker(\sigma) & \rightarrow & \ker(\beta) & \rightarrow & 0 \rightarrow 0 \\ & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ 0 & \rightarrow & M & \xrightarrow{\alpha} & E(M) & \rightarrow & E(M)/M \rightarrow 0 \\ & & \downarrow \sigma & & \downarrow \beta & & \parallel \\ 0 & \rightarrow & K & \xrightarrow{f} & L & \rightarrow & E(M)/M \rightarrow 0 \\ & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ & & 0 & & 0 & & 0 \end{array}$$

Hence $\ker(\sigma) \simeq \ker(\beta)$ by the 3×3 Lemma [10, Exercise 6.16, p.175]. This completes the proof.

It is well known that if R is a left n -coherent ring, then every right R -module has a $(n, 0)$ -flat preenvelope (see [13]). Here we have

Proposition 6 Let R be a left n -coherent ring.

(1) If L is a cokernel of a $(n, 0)$ -flat preenvelope $f : K \rightarrow F$ of a right R -module K , where F is flat, then L is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat.

(2) If M is an n -presented $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module, then M is a cokernel of an $(n, 0)$ -flat preenvelope.

Proof (1) There is an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow \text{im}(f) \xrightarrow{i} F \rightarrow L \rightarrow 0$. It is clear that $i : \text{im}(f) \rightarrow F$ is an $(n, 0)$ -flat preenvelope. For any $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module N , N^+ is $(n, 0)$ -flat by [14, Theorem 2.15]. Thus we obtain an exact

sequence

$$\text{Hom}(F, N^+) \longrightarrow \text{Hom}(\text{im}(f), N^+) \longrightarrow 0,$$

which yields the exactness of $(F \otimes N)^+ \longrightarrow (\text{im}(f) \otimes N)^+ \longrightarrow 0$. So the sequence $0 \longrightarrow \text{im}(f) \otimes N \longrightarrow F \otimes N$ is exact. But the flatness of F implies the exactness of $0 = \text{Tor}_1(F, N) \longrightarrow \text{Tor}_1(L, N) \longrightarrow \text{im}(f) \otimes N \longrightarrow F \otimes N$, and hence $\text{Tor}_1(L, N) = 0$.

(2) Let M be an n -presented $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module. There is an exact sequence $0 \longrightarrow K \longrightarrow P \longrightarrow M \longrightarrow 0$ with P finitely generated projective and K is $(n-1)$ -presented. We claim that $K \longrightarrow P$ is an $(n, 0)$ -flat preenvelope. In fact, for any $(n, 0)$ -flat right R -module F , we have $\text{Tor}_1(M, F^+) = 0$, and so we get the following commutative diagram with the first row exact:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} 0 & \longrightarrow & K \otimes F^+ & \xrightarrow{\alpha} & P \otimes F^+ \\ & & \downarrow \tau_{K,F} & & \downarrow \tau_{P,F} \\ & & \text{Hom}(K, F)^+ & \xrightarrow{\theta} & \text{Hom}(P, F)^+ \end{array}$$

Note that $\tau_{K,F}$ is an epimorphism and $\tau_{P,F}$ is an isomorphism by [2, Lemma 2]. Thus θ is a monomorphism, and hence $\text{Hom}(P, F) \longrightarrow \text{Hom}(K, F)$ is epic, as required.

We shall say that a right R -module M is strongly $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat if $\text{Tor}_i(M, G) = 0$ for all $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -modules G and all $i \geq 1$. Similarly, a left R -module N will be called strongly $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective if $\text{Ext}^i(G, N) = 0$ for all $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -modules G and all $i \geq 1$.

Theorem 2 Let R be a left and right n -coherent ring. Consider the following conditions:

- (1) $(n, 0)\text{-id}(R_R) \leq 1$.
- (2) Every submodule of an $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module, which factor module is n -presented, is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat.
- (3) Every n -presented $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module is strongly $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat.
- (4) Every $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module is strongly $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective.
- (5) Every quotient of an $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective.

Then (1) \Rightarrow (2) \Rightarrow (3) \Leftarrow (4) \Leftarrow (5).

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let A be a submodule of an $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module B such that B/A is n -presented and M an $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module. Then one gets an exact sequence $\text{Tor}_2(B/A, M) \longrightarrow \text{Tor}_1(A, M) \longrightarrow \text{Tor}_1(B, M) = 0$. On the other hand, there is a pure exact sequence $0 \longrightarrow M \longrightarrow \prod (R_R)^+$ since $(R_R)^+$ is a cogenerator in $R\text{-Mod}$. Thus we get a split exact sequence $(\prod (R_R)^+)^+ \longrightarrow M^+ \longrightarrow 0$. Note that $(n, 0)\text{-fd}((R_R)^+) = (n, 0)\text{-id}(R_R) \leq 1$ by [14, Theorem 2.15], and so $(n, 0)\text{-fd}(\prod (R_R)^+) \leq 1$ since R is right n -coherent. It follows that $(n, 0)\text{-id}((\prod (R_R)^+)^+) = (n, 0)\text{-fd}(\prod (R_R)^+) \leq 1$ by [14, Theorem 2.15]. Hence $(n, 0)\text{-fd}(M) = (n, 0)\text{-id}(M^+) \leq 1$. Thus $\text{Tor}_2(B/A, M) = 0$ by the condition, and so $\text{Tor}_1(A, M) = 0$. Therefore, A is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Let M be an n -presented $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module. Then there is an exact sequence $0 \longrightarrow K \longrightarrow P \longrightarrow M \longrightarrow 0$ with P projective. So K is $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat by (2). Thus M is strongly $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat by induction.

(5) \Rightarrow (4) Let M be an $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module. Then there is an exact sequence $0 \longrightarrow M \longrightarrow E \longrightarrow L \longrightarrow 0$ with E injective. So L is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective by (5). It is easy to check that M is strongly $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective by induction.

(4) \Rightarrow (3) holds by Remark 2 and the standard isomorphism: $\text{Ext}^n(N, M^+) \simeq \text{Tor}_n(M, N)^+$ for any right R -module M , any left R -module N and any $n \geq 1$ (see [10, p.360]).

Recall that a short exact sequence of right R -modules $0 \longrightarrow A \longrightarrow B \longrightarrow C \longrightarrow 0$ is called n -pure if every n -presented right R -module is projective with respect to this sequence [14]. In this case, A is said to be an n -pure submodule of B . It is easy to see that the pure exact sequence is 1-pure exact in this definition, and the pure exact sequence must be n -pure. Let A be a pure submodule of the right R -module B , A must be an n -pure submodule of B .

Proposition 7 A left $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective R -module N is $(n, 0)$ -injective if and only if, for every n -presented left R -module M , every homomorphism $f : M \longrightarrow L$ factors through an injective left R -module, where L is a cokernel of injective envelope of N .

Proof "Only if" part. There is an exact sequence $0 \longrightarrow N \longrightarrow E(N) \xrightarrow{\pi} L \longrightarrow 0$ with E injective. Since the exact sequence is n -pure, there exists $g : M \longrightarrow E$ such that $\pi g = f$, as required.

"If" part. It is enough to show that the exact sequence $0 \longrightarrow N \xrightarrow{i} E(N) \xrightarrow{\pi} L \longrightarrow 0$ is n -pure by [14, Theorem 2.2]. Let M be any n -presented right R -module. For any $f : M \longrightarrow L$, there exist an injective left R -module Q and $g : M \longrightarrow Q$ and $h : Q \longrightarrow L$ such that $f = hg$ by hypothesis. Note that $E(N) \xrightarrow{\pi} L$ is a precover of L , since N is FI-injective by Proposition 4. Thus there exists $\alpha : Q \longrightarrow E(N)$ such that $h = \pi\alpha$, and so $f = \pi\alpha g$. Therefore we get an exact sequence $\text{Hom}(M, E(N)) \longrightarrow \text{Hom}(M, L) \longrightarrow 0$. So N is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

III. $(n, 0)$ -INJECTIVE DIMENSIONS AND THE LEFT DERIVED FUNCTORS OF HOM

As is mentioned in the introduction, if R is a left n -coherent ring, then $\text{Hom}(-, -)$ is left balanced on ${}_R\mathcal{M} \times_R \mathcal{M}$ by $n\text{-FI} \times n\text{-FI}$. Let $\text{Ext}_n(-, -)$ denote the n th left derived functor of $\text{Hom}(-, -)$ with respect to the pair $n\text{-FI} \times n\text{-FI}$. Then, for two left R -modules M and N , $\text{Ext}_n(M, N)$ can be computed using a right $n\text{-FI}$ -resolution of M or a left $n\text{-FI}$ -resolution of N .

Let $0 \longrightarrow M \xrightarrow{g} F^0 \xrightarrow{f} F^1 \longrightarrow \dots$ be a right $n\text{-FI}$ -resolution of M . Applying $\text{Hom}(-, N)$, we obtain the deleted complex $\dots \longrightarrow \text{Hom}(F^1, N) \xrightarrow{f^*} \text{Hom}(F^0, N) \longrightarrow 0$. Then $\text{Ext}_n(M, N)$ exactly the n th homology of the complex above. There is a canonical map $\sigma :$

$$\text{Ext}_0(M, N) = \text{Hom}(F^0, N) / \text{im}(f^*) \longrightarrow \text{Hom}(M, N)$$

defined by $\sigma(\alpha + \text{im}(f^*)) = \alpha g$ for $\alpha \in \text{Hom}(F^0, N)$.

Proposition 8 Let R be a left n -coherent ring. The following are equivalent for a left R -module M :

- (1) M is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(2) The canonical map $\sigma : \text{Ext}_0(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, N)$ is an epimorphism for any left R - module N .

(3) The canonical map $\sigma : \text{Ext}_0(M, M) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, M)$ is an epimorphism.

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2) is obvious by letting $F^0 = M$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) is trivial.

(3) \Rightarrow (1). By (3), there exists $\alpha \in \text{Hom}(F^0, M)$ such that $\sigma(\alpha + \text{im}(f^*)) = \alpha g = 1_M$. Thus M is isomorphic to a direct summand of F^0 , and hence it is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

Corollary 2 The following are equivalent for a left n -coherent ring R .

(1) ${}_R R$ is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(2) The canonical map $\sigma : \text{Ext}_0({}_R R, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}({}_R R, N)$ is an epimorphism for any left R - module N .

(3) The canonical map $\sigma : \text{Ext}_0({}_R R, {}_R R) \rightarrow \text{Hom}({}_R R, {}_R R)$ is an epimorphism.

(4) Every (n) -presented left R -module has an epic $(n, 0)$ -injective cover.

(5) Every (n) -presented right R -module has a monic $(n, 0)$ -flat preenvelope.

(6) Every (n) -presented right R -module is a submodule of a $(n, 0)$ -flat right R -module.

Proof (1) \Leftrightarrow (2) \Leftrightarrow (3) follow from Proposition 8.

(1) \Rightarrow (4). Let M be a left R -module, then M has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover g . On the other hand, there is an exact sequence $F \rightarrow M \rightarrow 0$ with F free. Since F is $(n, 0)$ -injective by (1), g is an epimorphism.

(4) \Rightarrow (1). Let $f : N \rightarrow_R R$ be an epic $(n, 0)$ -injective cover. Then ${}_R R$ is isomorphic to a direct summand of N , and so ${}_R R$ is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(1) \Leftrightarrow (5). by [13, Theorem 4.5]

(5) \Rightarrow (6) is obvious.

(6) \Rightarrow (5) follows since R is a left n -coherent ring and by [13, Proposition 4.1].

Proposition 9 Let R be a left n -coherent ring. Then the following are equivalent for a left R - module M :

(1) right n - \mathcal{FI} -dim $M \leq 1$.

(2) The canonical map $\sigma : \text{Ext}_0(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, N)$ is a monomorphism for any left R - module N .

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2). By (1), M has a right n - \mathcal{FI} -resolution $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow 0$. Thus we get an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F^1, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F^0, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, N)$ for any left R -module N . Hence σ is a monomorphism.

(2) \Rightarrow (1). Consider the exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow L^1 \rightarrow 0$, where $M \rightarrow F^0$ is an $(n, 0)$ -injective preenvelope. We only need to show that L^1 is $(n, 0)$ -injective. By [6, Theorem 8.2.3], we have the commutative diagram with exact rows:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} \text{Ext}_0(L^1, L^1) & \longrightarrow & \text{Ext}_0(F^0, L^1) & & \\ & & \downarrow \sigma_1 & & \downarrow \sigma_2 \\ 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(L^1, L^1) & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(F^0, L^1) \\ & & \downarrow \sigma_3 & & \\ & \longrightarrow & \text{Ext}_0(M, L^1) & \longrightarrow & 0 \\ & & \downarrow \sigma_3 & & \\ & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(M, L^1) & & \end{array}$$

Note that σ_2 is an epimorphism by Proposition 8 and σ_3 is a monomorphism by (2). Hence σ_1 is an epimorphism by the

Snake Lemma [10, Theorem 6.5]. Thus L^1 is $(n, 0)$ -injective by Proposition 8, and so (1) follows.

Lemma 1 Let R be a left n -coherent ring. Then

(1) right n - \mathcal{FI} -dim $(M) = (n, 0)$ -id (M) for any left R -module M ;

(2) $(n, 0)$ -wdim $(R) = 1, (n, 0)$ -dim $(R) = \text{gl right } n$ - \mathcal{FI} -dim \mathcal{M} .

Proof (1) It is clear that $(n, 0)$ -id $(M) \leq$ right n - \mathcal{FI} -dim M . Conversely, we may assume that $(n, 0)$ -id $(M) = m < \infty$. Let $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow F^{m-1} \rightarrow F^m \rightarrow 0$ be a partial right n - \mathcal{FI} -resolution of M . Then we get an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow F^{m-1} \rightarrow L \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, L is $(n, 0)$ -injective by [14, Theorem 2.12], and so right n - \mathcal{FI} -dim $M \leq m$, as desired.

(2) follows from [14, Theorem 2.15] and (1).

Lemma 2 ([7]) Let \mathcal{C} be a class of R -modules and M an R -module.

(1) If $F \rightarrow M$ and $G \rightarrow M$ are \mathcal{C} -precovers with kernels K and L , respectively, then $K \oplus G \simeq L \oplus F$.

(2) If $M \rightarrow F$ and $M \rightarrow G$ are \mathcal{C} -preenvelopes with cokernels K and L , respectively, then $K \oplus G \simeq L \oplus F$.

Recall that a left R is called left n -hereditary [14] if every $(n-1)$ -presented submodule of projective left R -module is projective.

Clearly, a ring R is left semihereditary if and only if it is right 1-hereditary. Left n -hereditary ring is left $(n+1)$ -hereditary.

Lemma 3 ([14]) The following statements are equivalent for a ring R :

(1) R is left n -hereditary.

(2) R is left n -coherent and $l.(n, 0)$ -dim $(R) \leq 1$.

(3) Factor module of $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(4) Factor module of injective left R -module is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(5) R is a right $(n, 1)$ -ring.

Theorem 3 The following are equivalent for a left n -coherent ring R :

(1) R is a left n -hereditary ring (i.e. $l.(n, 0)$ -dim $(R) \leq 1$).

(2) The canonical map $\sigma : \text{Ext}_0(M, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, N)$ is monic for all left R -modules M and N .

(3) Every left R -module has a monic $(n, 0)$ -injective cover.

(4) Every $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module is injective.

(5) Every $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective left R -module is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(6) Every (n) -presented $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module is flat.

(7) The kernel of any $(n, 0)$ -injective (pre)cover of a left R -module is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(8) The cokernel of any $(n, 0)$ -injective preenvelope of a left R -module is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(9) The kernel of any $(n, 0)$ -flat (pre)cover of a right R -module is flat.

Proof (1) \Leftrightarrow (2) holds by Proposition 9 and Lemma 1.

(1) \Rightarrow (4) follows from Proposition 3 and Lemma 1.

(4) \Rightarrow (5) is trivial.

(5) \Rightarrow (6). Let M be an $(n, 0)$ -FI-flat right R -module. Then M^+ is $(n, 0)$ -FI-injective by Remark 1, and hence M^+ is

$(n, 0)$ -injective by (5). So M is $(n, 0)$ -flat by [14, Theorem 2.15].

(1) \Rightarrow (3) follows from Lemma 3 and [13, Proposition 4.9].

(3) \Rightarrow (7). Let $f : F \rightarrow M$ be an $(n, 0)$ -injective precover of a left R -module M and $K = \ker(f)$. Since there exists a monic $(n, 0)$ -injective cover $g : G \rightarrow M$ by (3), we have $K \oplus G \simeq F$ by Lemma 2(1). So K is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

(7) \Rightarrow (1). It is enough to show that any quotient of an $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module is $(n, 0)$ -injective. But it is clear by Lemma 2.

(1) \Leftrightarrow (8) follows from Lemma 1.

(1) \Leftrightarrow (9) is obvious.

Theorem 4 Let R be a left n -coherent ring and an integer $m \geq 2$. The following are equivalent for a left R -module M :

(1) right n - \mathcal{FT} -dim $M \leq m$.

(2) $\text{Ext}_{m+k}(M, N) = 0$ for all left R -modules N and all $k \geq -1$.

(3) $\text{Ext}_{m-1}(M, N) = 0$ for all left R -modules N .

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2). Let $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow F^m \rightarrow 0$ be a right n - \mathcal{FT} -resolution of M , which induces an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F^m, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F^{m-1}, N) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F^{m-2}, N) \rightarrow \dots$ for any left R -module N . Hence $\text{Ext}_m(M, N) = \text{Ext}_{m-1}(M, N) = 0$. Note that it is clear that $\text{Ext}_{m+k}(M, N) = 0$ for all $k \geq 1$. Then (2) holds.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) is trivial.

(3) \Rightarrow (1). Let $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow F^{m-2} \xrightarrow{f} F^{m-1} \xrightarrow{g} F^m \rightarrow \dots$ be a right n - \mathcal{FT} -resolution of M , with $L^m = \text{coker}(F_{m-2} \rightarrow F_{m-1})$. We only need to show that L^m is $(n, 0)$ -injective. In fact, we have the exact sequence $F^{m-1} \xrightarrow{\pi} L^m \rightarrow 0$ and $0 \rightarrow L^m \xrightarrow{\lambda} F^{m-1}$ such that $g = \lambda\pi$ by (3), $\text{Ext}_{m-1}(M, L^m) = 0$. Thus the sequence $0 \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F^m, L^m) \xrightarrow{g^*} \text{Hom}(F_{m-1}, L^m) \xrightarrow{f^*} \text{Hom}(F^{m-2}, L^m) \rightarrow \dots$ is exact. Since $f^*(\pi) = \pi f = 0$, $\pi \in \ker(f^*) = \text{im}(g^*)$. Thus there exists $h \in \text{Hom}(F^m, L^m)$ such that $\pi = g^*(h) = hg = h\lambda\pi$, and hence $h\lambda = 1$ since π is epic. Therefore L^m is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

Corollary 3 The following are equivalent for a left n -coherent ring R and an integer $m \geq 2$:

(1) $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R) \leq m$.

(2) $\text{Ext}_{m+k}(M, N) = 0$ for all left R -modules M and N , and all $k \geq -1$.

(3) $\text{Ext}_{m-1}(M, N) = 0$ for all left R -modules M and N .

Proof It follows from Lemma 1 and Theorem 4.

It has been proven that R is a left coherent ring and $l.\text{FP-dim}(R) \leq 2$ if and only if every right R -module has an FP-injective cover with the unique mapping property. Now we have

Theorem 5 The following are equivalent for a ring R :

(1) R is left n -coherent and $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R) \leq 2$.

(2) Every left R -module has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover with the unique mapping property.

(3) R is left n -coherent and $\text{Ext}_1(M, N) = 0$ for all left R -modules M and N .

(4) R is left n -coherent and $\text{Ext}_k(M, N) = 0$ for all left R -modules M, N and all $k \geq 1$.

Proof (1) \Leftrightarrow (3) \Leftrightarrow (4) follow from Corollary 3.

(1) \Rightarrow (2). Let M be any left R -module. Then M has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover $f : F \rightarrow M$. It is enough to

show that, for any $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module G and any homomorphism $g : G \rightarrow F$ such that $fg = 0$, we have $g = 0$. In fact, there exists $\beta : F/\text{im}(g) \rightarrow M$ such that $\beta\pi = f$ since $\text{im}(g) \subseteq \ker(f)$, where $\pi : F \rightarrow F/\text{im}(g)$ is the natural map. Since $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R) \leq 2$, $F/\text{im}(g)$ is $(n, 0)$ -injective. Thus there exists $\alpha : F/\text{im}(g) \rightarrow F$ such that $\beta = f\alpha$, and so we get the commutative diagram with an exact row:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} G & \xrightarrow{g} & F & \xleftarrow{\pi} & F/\text{im}(g) & \rightarrow & 0 \\ & \searrow^0 & \downarrow f & \swarrow \beta & & & \\ & & M & & & & \end{array}$$

Thus $f\alpha\pi = f$, and hence $\alpha\pi$ is an isomorphism. Therefore, π is monic, and so $g = 0$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1). We first prove that R is a left n -coherent ring. Let $\{C_i, \varphi_j^i\}$ be a direct system with each C_i $(n, 0)$ -injective. By hypothesis, $\lim_{\rightarrow} C_i$ has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover $\alpha : E \rightarrow \lim_{\rightarrow} C_i$ with the unique mapping property. Let $\alpha_i : C_i \rightarrow \lim_{\rightarrow} C_i$ satisfy $\alpha_i = \alpha_j \varphi_j^i$ whenever $i \leq j$. Then there exists $f_i : C_i \rightarrow E$ such that $\alpha_i = \alpha f_i$ for any i . It follows that $\alpha f_i = \alpha f_j \varphi_j^i$, and so $f_i = f_j \varphi_j^i$ whenever $i \leq j$. Therefore, by the definition of direct limits, there exists $\beta : \lim_{\rightarrow} C_i \rightarrow E$ such that $f_i = \beta \alpha_i$ and $f_j = \beta \alpha_j$. Thus $(\alpha\beta)\alpha_i = \alpha(\beta\alpha_i) = \alpha f_i = \alpha_i$ for any i . Therefore $\alpha\beta = 1_{\lim_{\rightarrow} C_i}$, by the definition of direct limits, and hence $\lim_{\rightarrow} C_i$ is a direct summand of E . So $\lim_{\rightarrow} C_i$ is $(n, 0)$ -injective. Thus R is a left n -coherent ring by [1].

Next we prove that $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R) \leq 2$. Let M be any left R -module. Then M has an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover $f : F \rightarrow M$ with the unique mapping property. So $0 \rightarrow F \rightarrow M \rightarrow 0$ is a left n - \mathcal{FT} -resolution. Thus $gl\text{-}n\text{-}\mathcal{FT}\text{-dim}_R M = 0$, and hence $l.(n, 0)\text{-dim}(R) \leq 2$ by Corollary 3.

Proposition 10 Let R be a left n -coherent ring. If M is an n -pure-injective left R -module, then $(n, 0)\text{-id}(M) \leq m$ ($m \geq 0$) if and only if for the minimal left n - \mathcal{FT} -resolution $\dots \rightarrow F_m \rightarrow F_{m-1} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow F_1 \rightarrow F_0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow 0$ of all n -pure-injective left R -module N , $\text{Hom}(M, F_m) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, K_m)$ is an epimorphism.

Proof The proof is modeled on that of [6, Lemma 8.4.34].

We will proceed by induction on m . Let $m = 0$. If M is $(n, 0)$ -injective, it is clear that $\text{Hom}(M, F_0) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, K_0)$ is an epimorphism, since $F_0 \rightarrow N$ is an $(n, 0)$ -injective cover of N . Conversely, put $N = M$. Then $\text{Hom}(M, F_0) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, M)$ is an epimorphism, and so M is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

Let $m \geq 1$. There is an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow E \rightarrow L \rightarrow 0$ with E injective. Then we have the following exact commutative diagrams:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc} \text{Hom}(E, F_n) & \rightarrow & \text{Hom}(E, K_n) & \rightarrow & 0 \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \\ \text{Hom}(M, F_n) & \rightarrow & \text{Hom}(M, K_n) & & \\ \downarrow & & & & \\ 0 & & & & \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 & & 0 & & 0 & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \\
 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(L, K_m) & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(L, F_{m-1}) & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \\
 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(E, K_m) & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(E, F_{m-1}) & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \\
 0 & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(M, K_m) & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(M, F_{m-1}) & & \\
 & & & & \downarrow & & \\
 & & & & 0 & & \\
 & & & & & & \\
 & & 0 & & & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & & & \\
 & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(L, K_{m-1}) & & & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & & & \\
 & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(E, K_{m-1}) & \longrightarrow & 0 & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & & & \\
 & \longrightarrow & \text{Hom}(M, K_{m-1}) & & & &
 \end{array}$$

Thus $(n, 0)\text{-id}(M) \leq m$ if and only if $(n, 0)\text{-id}(L) \leq m - 1$ by [14, Theorem 2.12.], if and only if $\text{Hom}(L, F_{m-1}) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(L, K_{m-1})$ is an epimorphism by induction if and only if $\text{Hom}(E, K_m) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, K_m)$ is an epimorphism by the second diagram if and only if $\text{Hom}(M, F_m) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(M, K_m)$ is an epimorphism by the first diagram.

IV. $(n, 0)$ -INJECTIVE DIMENSIONS AND THE RIGHT DERIVED FUNCTORS OF TOR

In this section, we introduce the right derived functors of Tor. If R is n -coherent, the $- \otimes -$ on $\mathcal{M}_R \times_R \mathcal{M}$ is right balanced by $n\text{-}\mathcal{F} \times n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$, where $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ stands for the class of all $(n, 0)$ -flat modules. In fact, we need to show that if $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots$ is a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ -resolution, which exists by [13, Lemma 4.1], and G is an $(n, 0)$ -injective left R -module, then $0 \rightarrow M \otimes G \rightarrow F^0 \otimes G \rightarrow F^1 \otimes G \rightarrow \dots$ is exact. Applying the functor $\text{Hom}_Z(-, Q/Z)$ and using a standard identity we see the sequence $0 \leftarrow \text{Hom}(M, G^+) \leftarrow \text{Hom}(F^0, G^+) \leftarrow \text{Hom}(F^1, G^+) \leftarrow \dots$. But G^+ is $(n, 0)$ -flat by [14, Theorem 2.15] and so this sequence is exact. This means the desired sequence is exact. Since right $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ -resolutions are exact, let $0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow G^0 \rightarrow G^1 \rightarrow \dots$ of a left R -module N , then $\dots \rightarrow G^{1+} \rightarrow G^{0+} \rightarrow N^+ \rightarrow 0$ is a left $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ -resolution. So applying the functor $\text{Hom}(F, -)$ to above sequence, we get the exact sequence $\dots \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F, G^{1+}) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F, G^{0+}) \rightarrow \text{Hom}(F, N^+) \rightarrow 0$ for $F \in n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$. Using a standard identity we get the exact sequence $0 \rightarrow F \otimes N \rightarrow F \otimes G^0 \rightarrow F \otimes G^1 \rightarrow \dots$.

Let $\text{Tor}^n(-, -)$ denote the n th right derived functor of $- \otimes -$ with respect to the pair $n\text{-}\mathcal{F} \times n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$. Then, for two left R -modules M and N , $\text{Tor}^n(M, N)$ can be computed using a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ -resolution of M or a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ -resolution of N .

Lemma 4 If $M_1 \rightarrow M_2 \rightarrow M_3 \rightarrow M_4$ is an exact sequence of left R -modules such that for every n -presented right R -module P , $P \otimes M_1 \rightarrow P \otimes M_2 \rightarrow P \otimes M_3 \rightarrow P \otimes M_4$ is exact, then $K = \ker(M_3 \rightarrow M_4)$ is an n -pure submodule of M_3 .

Proof $P \otimes M_1 \rightarrow P \otimes M_2 \rightarrow P \otimes M_3 \rightarrow P \otimes M_4$ is exact and $P \otimes K \rightarrow P \otimes M_3 \rightarrow P \otimes M_4$ is a complex. Thus exactness of the first sequence means $0 \rightarrow P \otimes K \rightarrow P \otimes M_3$ is exact. This means K is an n -pure submodule of M_3 .

Theorem 6 Let R be a left n -coherent ring and an integer $m \geq 2$. The following are equivalent for a left R -module N :

- (1) right $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}\text{-dim } N \leq m$.
- (2) $\text{Tor}^{m+k}(M, N) = 0$ for all right R -modules M and all $k \geq -1$.
- (3) $\text{Tor}^m(M, N) = \text{Tor}^{m-1}(M, N) = 0$ for all right R -modules M .
- (4) $\text{Tor}^m(M, N) = \text{Tor}^{m-1}(M, N) = 0$ for all right n -presented R -modules M .

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let $0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow A^0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow A^n \rightarrow 0$ be a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ -resolution of N . Then $M \otimes A^{n-2} \rightarrow M \otimes A^{n-1} \rightarrow M \otimes A^n \rightarrow 0$ is exact and so $\text{Tor}^{m-1}(M, N) = \text{Tor}^m(M, N) = 0$. But clearly $\text{Tor}^{m+k}(M, N) = 0$ for $k \geq -1$. Hence (2) holds.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) \Rightarrow (4) is trivial.

(4) \Rightarrow (1). Let $0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow A^0 \rightarrow A^1 \rightarrow \dots$ be a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ -resolution of N . Then for any n -presented R -module M , $M \otimes A^{n-2} \rightarrow M \otimes A^{n-1} \rightarrow M \otimes A^n \rightarrow M \otimes A^{n+1}$ is exact. So by Lemma 4, $K = \ker(A^n \rightarrow A^{n+1})$ is n -pure in A^n . But an n -pure submodule of $(n, 0)$ -injective module is $(n, 0)$ -injective by [14, Proposition 2.2]. But then $0 \rightarrow N \rightarrow A^0 \rightarrow A^1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow A^{n-1} \rightarrow K \rightarrow 0$ is a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ -resolution of N and (1) holds.

Theorem 7 Let R be a left n -coherent ring and an integer $m \geq 2$. The following are equivalent for a left R -module N :

- (1) right $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}\text{-dim } M \leq m$.
- (2) $\text{Tor}^{m+k}(M, N) = 0$ for all right R -modules N and all $k \geq -1$.
- (3) $\text{Tor}^m(M, N) = \text{Tor}^{m-1}(M, N) = 0$ for all right R -modules N .

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (2) \Rightarrow (3) is trivial.

(3) \Rightarrow (1). Let $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots$ be a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ -resolution of N . Then for any R -module N , $F^{n-2} \otimes N \rightarrow F^{n-1} \otimes N \rightarrow F^n \otimes N \rightarrow F^{n+1} \otimes N$ is exact. So by Lemma 4, $K = \ker(F^n \rightarrow F^{n+1})$ is n -pure in F^n and so is $(n, 0)$ -flat. But $F^{n-2} \rightarrow F^{n-1} \rightarrow K \rightarrow 0$ is exact. Therefore, $L = \ker(F^{n-2} \rightarrow F^{n-1})$ is n -pure in F^{n-2} and so is $(n, 0)$ -flat by [14, Corollary 2.20]. But then $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow F^{n-3} \rightarrow L \rightarrow 0$ is a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ -resolution of M and so (1) holds.

Theorem 8 Let R be a left n -coherent ring and an integer $m \geq 0$. The following are equivalent

- (1) For every $(n, 0)$ -flat left R -module F , there is an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow F \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow E^m \rightarrow 0$ with each E^i is $(n, 0)$ -injective.
- (2) If $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots$ is a right $n\text{-}\mathcal{F}$ -resolution of M , then the sequence is exact at F^k for $k \geq m - 1$, where $F^{-1} = M$.
- (3) There is an exact sequence $0 \rightarrow R \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow E^m \rightarrow 0$ of left R -module with each E^i is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

Proof (1) \Rightarrow (3) is immediate.

(3) \Rightarrow (2) We recall that $-\otimes-$ is right balanced on $\mathcal{M}_R \times_R \mathcal{M}$ by $n\text{-}\mathcal{F} \times n\text{-}\mathcal{FI}$ with right derived functors $\text{Tor}^k(-, -)$.

If $m \geq 2$, using the exact sequence $0 \rightarrow R \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow E^m \rightarrow 0$, we get $\text{Tor}^k(M, R) = 0$ for $k \geq m - 1$. Computing using $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots$ as in (2), we see that $\text{Tor}^k(M, R)$ is just the k th homology group of this complex, giving the desired result.

For $m = 1, 0 \rightarrow R \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow E^1 \rightarrow 0$ exact sequence gives $\text{Tor}^1(M, R) = 0$ so that, as above, $F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow F^2$ is exact and $M \otimes R \rightarrow \text{Tor}^0(M, R)$ is onto. computing the latter morphism using $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1$ is exact.

If $m = 0$ then (3) means R is $(n, 0)$ -injective as a left R -module. But the balance of $-\otimes-$ then gives $0 \rightarrow M \otimes R \rightarrow F^0 \otimes R \rightarrow F^1 \otimes R \rightarrow \dots$ is exact. That is $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots$ is exact.

(2) \Rightarrow (1). Assume (2) with $m \geq 2$. Let $0 \rightarrow F \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow E^m \rightarrow 0$ with each E^i is $(n, 0)$ -injective. Then by (2), we get $\text{Tor}^k(M, F) = 0$ for $k \geq m - 1$ since F is $(n, 0)$ -flat. Computing using $0 \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow E^1 \rightarrow \dots$ and using the Lemma 4, we get $K = \ker(E^m \rightarrow E^{m+1})$ is n -pure in A^m and so K is also $(n, 0)$ -injective. Hence $0 \rightarrow F \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow E^{m-1} \rightarrow K \rightarrow 0$ gives the desired exact sequence.

Now let $m = 1$. Then (2) says $M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots$ is exact. So $\text{Tor}^k(M, F) = 0$ for $k = 0$ and $M \otimes F \rightarrow \text{Tor}^0(M, F)$ is onto. Hence if $0 \rightarrow F \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow E^1 \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow 0$ is exact, $M \otimes F \rightarrow M \otimes E^0 \rightarrow M \otimes E^1 \rightarrow M \otimes E^2$ is exact for all n -presented M . By Lemma 25, we again get the desired exact sequence $0 \rightarrow F \rightarrow E^0 \rightarrow K \rightarrow 0$ with $K = \ker(E^1 \rightarrow E^2)$.

If $m = 0$ then $0 \rightarrow M \rightarrow F^0 \rightarrow F^1 \rightarrow \dots$ exact means $\text{Tor}^k(M, F) = 0$ for $k > 0$ and $M \otimes F \rightarrow \text{Tor}^0(M, F)$ is isomorphism. This gives that $0 \rightarrow M \otimes F \rightarrow M \otimes E^0 \rightarrow M \otimes E^1$ is exact for all M which implies F is an n -pure submodule of E^0 and so is $(n, 0)$ -injective.

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